

PEDAGOGICAL FUNDAMENTALS OF TARGETED TRAINING OF GIFTED STUDENTS IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: This article discusses the pedagogical basis, content, form, factors of targeted training of talented youth in Uzbekistan and provides a statement of conclusions and recommendations for its improvement.

Key words: Talent, ability, pedagogical basis, pedagogical form, motivation, intellect, creativity, development.

During the years of independence, special attention was paid to stimulating youth talent as one of the main principles of state policy in the field of education in Uzbekistan. Of particular importance is the training, assistance to young people with intellectual potential who develop the scientific and creative potential of our republic, the ability to show, develop their natural abilities in areas related to talent holders and in specific areas of Science and create opportunities for the realization of unique talent in them.

Urgent tasks such as "creation of a system for the implementation of work with talented and talented young people aimed at a specific goal" were established. In this process, work is being carried out to ensure transparency in the identification of the most capable and educated students-young people, expand the network of specialized general education institutions, which are taught in depth in such important and high-demand subjects as foreign languages, mathematics, physics, chemistry, biology, attract the pedagogical community with scientific potential to work with gifted children inBecause, the emergence of the talent of each child is not just for a separate person, perhaps it is the factors necessary for society and its progress.

Giftedness is the quality of systematic development of the human psyche throughout life, determined by the fact that a person has the opportunity to achieve one or more high results in relation to other people. A gifted student has individual potential, distinguished from other students by his intellectual level, cognitive capabilities, ability. If this potential is not identified in time, if it is not developed, then a unique talent endowed by nature will not come true in them. "To support and encourage talented and talented young people" is today's most pressing task. In order to develop giftedness in young people, it is necessary to have knowledge about the components of giftedness.

Students have motivational, emotional volitional, intellectual, creative structural structures for the development of giftedness: motivational structure - consists of such qualities as motivation to have one's own Goya, ability to self-indulge, awareness of the personal importance of knowledge and skills.

Emotional volitional structure-consists of such qualities as volitional qualities, the ability to show goodwill and support, self-awareness, emotion management and emotional control. Intellectual structure-interest in knowledge, flexibility of thoughts, desire to know a

new one and activity on preparation, activity and research for it consist of qualities. Creative composition consists of such qualities as creative imagination, originality of ideas, search for new ways to solve problems, the ability to apply acquired knowledge in New conditions and die.

One of the important areas of development of the personality of a gifted student is cooperation, the purpose of which is to create conditions for the harmonious development of a gifted student. In this process, tasks such as preventing problems in student development, helping to solve the problems of student development education, socialization, improving the cooperation of students, fathers and teachers while familiarizing themselves with curricula are solved. In this process, it is important to take into account the importance of the relationship between parents and children, their mutual emotional unity, the acquisition of masterpieces of scientific knowledge and personality culture with the help of social influences, their manifestation in a special way in the socialization of students in connection with the age period. It is worth saying that in educational institutions "small academies", consisting of talented students:

- fanlarkesimidactidorlives;
- creatizementsworthy;
- in the field of literature, art, sports, impotents;
- research students;
- programmer (designer) direction students.

The establishment of "small academies" in educational institutions has a positive effect on the formation of students as a patriotic, perfect person who correctly understands and supports the internal and foreign policy of the state, while paying attention from childhood to the realization of their abilities. Of course, in this process, it is important to use socio-pedagogical technologies that contribute to the targeted training of gifted students." Establishing mutually beneficial cooperation of education with manufacturing enterprises and research institutes "also gives an effective result. Socio-pedagogical technologies for targeted training of gifted students are divided into 4:

1. Social psychological
2. Consultative
3. Bo effective organization of negative time
4. Ideological prophylactic

- Development of social psychological-emotional stability, development of social intelligence

- Consultative-to overcome social mental barriers, prevent conflicts, develop wisdom skills

- Effective organization of free time-Organization of work on information, formation of a culture of reading, development of creative imagination

- Ideological prophylactic-tolerance includes a technology that forms such qualities as the formation of holiness, the formation of social activity, self-defense against external influences.

The technologies listed above serve to give motivation to gifted students, to raise their intellectual potential, to exert an invaluable power in the formation of the quality of creativity in them. To do this, one of the main requirements for pedagogical teachers of Secondary Schools consists in early identification of gifted students, creation of the necessary conditions

for the development of talent in the desired direction, understanding the psyche of the student and providing qualified assistance. This in turn requires taking into account the following pedagogical factors when educating students:

1. Development of differentiated programs for working with gifted students in educational institutions
2. Giving special complex educational tasks for gifted students in the content of new generation textbooks, teaching aids, educational developments created for secondary schools
3. Achieving meaningful, consistent, systematic organization of free time of gifted students within the framework of five initiatives in secondary schools
4. Bo' lajak to ensure that teachers have competency to work with gifted students
5. Popularization of advanced work experiences with high performance of gifted students
6. Factors such as establishing the creative use of foreign experiences in working with gifted students.

All of the factors listed above are able to provide motivation to gifted students, raise their intellectual potential, form the quality of creativity in them and provide an assessment of their future maturation as a perfect, mature person.

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